

CLINICAL EFFICACY OF *SHODHITA KASISADRAVA BASTI* IN THE MANAGEMENT OF *ARSHA* (SECOND-DEGREE INTERNAL HAEMORRHOIDS): A CASE STUDY

Sagar Negi^{*1}, Bhabhor Savitribahen², Dr. Darshana Ramole³

^{1,2}Second Year P.G. Scholar, P.G. Department of Shalya Tantra, Shree Swaminarayan Ayurvedic College, Kalol, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

³Head of Department, Shalya Tantra Department, Shree Swaminarayan Ayurvedic College, Kalol, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Sagar Negi

Second Year P.G. Scholar, P.G.
Department of Shalya Tantra, Shree
Swaminarayan Ayurvedic College,
Kalol, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: *Arsha* is a common anorectal disorder characterized by swelling of the anal tissues, often associated with pain, bleeding, and prolapse. In Ayurvedic classics, *Arsha* is described as a *Tridoshaja Vyadhi*, predominantly involving *Apana Vata*. Second-degree internal haemorrhoids, which prolapse during defecation and reduce spontaneously are often managed with conservative approaches. The present study explores the efficacy of *Shodhita Kasisadrava Basti*, a medicated enema using purified *Kasisa* - as a novel intervention in the management of second-degree internal haemorrhoids (*Arsha*). **Methods:** A single case of a 36-year-old male patient presenting with classical signs of second-degree internal haemorrhoids, bleeding per rectum, and prolapse during defecation- was selected based on the diagnostic criteria: Clinical symptoms and Digital per rectal

examination. A total of 9 Basti were administered over 3 weeks (3 consecutive *Basti* per week), prepared using 5 *Ratti*(625mg) of *Shodhita Kasis Churna* dissolved in 30 ml distilled water. The patient was assessed on baseline, weekly intervals, and at a 45-day follow-up post-treatment for symptoms including bleeding, prolapse, itching and discomfort. **Results:** Marked improvement was observed after the completion of 9 *Basti*. Bleeding per rectum

ceased by the 6th *Basti*, and prolapse reduced significantly. Discomfort during defecation were alleviated. On 45-day follow-up, the patient reported no recurrence of or prolapse, and digital rectal examination revealed no significant internal bulge. No adverse reactions were noted during or after the intervention. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The use of *Shodhita Kasisadrava Basti* demonstrated promising results in reducing the clinical features of second-degree internal haemorrhoids(*Arsha*). The localized action of *Kasisa* on the vascular tissues and its *Shankochan* and *Lekhana* properties, when administered rectally, may help shrink the pile mass and alleviate symptoms without invasive procedures. This case study supports the potential of *Kasisadrava Basti* as a minimally invasive and effective Ayurvedic therapy for haemorrhoids, meriting larger clinical trials.

KEYWORDS: *Arsha*, *Shodhita Kasisadrava Basti*, Internal Haemorrhoids, *Basti Karma*.

INTRODUCTION

Acharya Sushruta has classified *Arsha* (haemorrhoids) as one of the *Ashtamahagada*, the eight most severe and challenging diseases.^[1] According to *Acharya Vagbhata*, *Arsha* (haemorrhoids) refers to muscular, fleshy growths in the anal region that obstruct the anal passage (*Guda Marga*) and harm a person like an enemy, ultimately affecting life and health.^[2] Haemorrhoids are characterized by the swelling of vascular structures within the haemorrhoidal plexus, located in the submucosal layer of the anal canal beneath the mucocutaneous lining. It is a prevalent condition of the anal region that can affect individuals of all genders.^[3]

Arsha, commonly referred to as "haemorrhoids", typically denotes a pathological enlargement of the haemorrhoidal veins caused by elevated pressure. It involves the dilation of the haemorrhoidal venous plexus along with an abnormally positioned and enlarged anal tissues, often presenting as a prolapsed or inflamed pile mass.^[4] This condition can cause bleeding, mucous discharge, and discomfort. Haemorrhoids are broadly categorized into two types: internal and external. Internal haemorrhoids form within the rectum, whereas external haemorrhoids arise beneath the skin surrounding the anus.^[5] Understanding about the causes, symptoms, and treatment options for *Arsha* is essential for those seeking relief from this condition. With appropriate medical advice, along with lifestyle and dietary changes, haemorrhoids can be effectively managed, helping individuals restore their comfort and quality of life. In more advanced cases, medical procedures like rubber band ligation, sclerotherapy, or surgical intervention may be required.^[6]

Extended periods of sitting or standing, excessive straining during defecation or urination, obesity, an unbalanced lifestyle, irregular dietary habits, pregnancy, and a sedentary routine contribute to the disturbance of *Jatharagni* and the aggravation of the *Tridosha*, particularly *Vata dosha*.^[7] *Shodhana Chikitsa* through *Basti Karma* (medicated enema) is highly effective for *Vata*-related disorders, and the use of *Kasis*, with its *Lekhana*, *Shodhana* and *Rakta-Stambhaka* properties, offers a promising therapeutic strategy.

PATIENT INFORMATION

- Age/Sex: 36 years / Male
- Occupation: Office worker
- Address: Ahmedabad, Gujarat

CHIEF COMPLAINTS

Complaint	Duration
Bleeding per rectum during defecation	4 months
Prolapse of pile mass during defecation (self-reducing)	3 months
Constipation	Intermittent

HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

A 36-year-old male presented with bleeding per rectum during defecation for 4 months, initially mild and occasional, later becoming frequent. For the past 3 months, he noted a self-reducing prolapse of a soft mass per anus during defecation. Intermittent constipation with hard stools and straining occurred 2–3 times weekly. No history of discharge, fever, weight loss, or similar complaints in the past.

PAST MEDICAL/SURGICAL HISTORY

- No history of diabetes, hypertension, or cardiac illness
- No surgical interventions in the anorectal region

PERSONAL AND DIETARY HABITS

- Sedentary lifestyle
- Irregular food habits with frequent intake of spicy and oily food
- Inadequate water intake
- Irregular bowel habits

EXAMINATION

General Examination

- Pulse: 76/min
- BP: 122/78 mmHg
- Weight: 66 kg
- No pallor or lymphadenopathy

Local Examination

- No external pile mass seen
- Proctoscopy: Internal pile masses palpable at 3 and 7 o'clock positions
- No signs of thrombosis or fissure

Lab Investigations

- CBC
- HIV I and II
- HBsAg
- RBS

DIAGNOSIS

Based on

1. **Clinical symptoms** – bleeding per rectum, prolapse
2. **Digital per rectal examination** findings Diagnosis – Second-degree internal haemorrhoids (*Arsha*)
3. **Lab Investigations** - CBC, HIV I & II, HBsAg, and RBS reports are all within normal limits.

SAMPRAPTI OF ARSHA

Acharya Sushruta explains the pathogenesis of *Arsha* as originating from the vitiation of *Doshas*, either individually, in dual combinations, or all three together, often accompanied by vitiated *Rakta*. These aggravated *Doshas* descend through the *Mahadhamani* and localize in the *Guda Pradesha* (anal region), particularly affecting the *Gudavalitraya*. This pathological process occurs especially in individuals with *Mandagni* and other contributing local factors, ultimately leading to the development of *Arsha*.^[8] *Acharya Charaka* states that *Arsha* arise due to the vitiation of all three *Doshas*. The disease progresses through both *Bahya* and

Abhyantara Rogamarga, ultimately involving the *Gudavalitraya*.^[9] According to *Acharya*.

Vagbhatta, the vitiation of *Doshas* causes impairment of *Agni (Mandagni)* and disturbance of *Apana Vayu*, leading to the accumulation and stagnation of *Mala* in the *Gudavali* (anal folds). The prolonged retention of *Mala* in this region eventually contributes to the formation of *Arshas* (haemorrhoids).^[10]

INTERVENTION

Shodhita Kasisadrava Basti^[11]

➤ *Kasisadrava* is mentioned in *Rastarnagini* for the management of *Arsha* as a *Basti* and said to give very excellent results. As ingredients of *Basti* get absorbed through mucosa and submucosa of rectum and anal canal and we will get expected result.

DRUG PREPARATION^[12]

- *Shodhita Kasis Churna*: 5 Ratti (625 mg)
- Mixed in 30 ml of distilled water, stirred until fully dissolved
- Prepared fresh each time before administration

Mode of drug administration

- The patient is placed in the left lateral position.
- The perianal region is cleaned using Betadine-soaked gauze.
- The area is then wiped dry with sterile gauze.
- LOX 2% jelly is applied to lubricate both:
 - The anal orifice, and
 - The tip of the red rubber catheter.
- A disposable syringe is filled with 30 ml of *Shodhita Kasisa Drava*.
- Air is removed from the syringe before administration.
- The catheter is gently inserted into the anus 3–4 cm deep.
- The medicine is then administered slowly through the syringe.
- After administration, the catheter is carefully withdrawn.
- The patient is advised to lie in the supine position for 30 minutes to ensure retention and optimal absorption.

Schedule

- Total 9 *Basti* given over 3 weeks

- 3 consecutive *Basti* per week (e.g., Monday–Wednesday)
- Given in *Kati Utthana* position in early morning

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

SYMPTOMS	0	1	2	3	SCORE
Bleeding	None	Occasional(1/week)	frequent(2-3/ week)	Daily	1
Prolapse	None	Rare, spontaneous reduction	With most stools	Minimal strain	2
Itching/ Discomfort	None	Mild	Moderate	Severe	2

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

SYMPTOMS	0 day	14 DAY	21 DAYS	45 DAYS
Bleeding	1	0	0	0
Prolapse	2	1	1	0
Itching/ Discomfort	2	1	0	0
TOTAL	5	2	1	0

FOLLOW UP: Day 45 Post-*Basti* Treatment.

OBSERVATIONS

- No second degree internal piles prolapse observed.
- No per rectal bleeding and itching, discomfort reported.
- Patient presents with mild constipation.
- Advised appropriate dietary regimen (*Pathya-Apathya*) and lifestyle corrections.
- Mild *Anulomana Dravyas* or supportive herbs (e.g., *Triphala*, *Eranda Sneha*, if required) may be introduced as per *Prakriti* and clinical judgment.

DISCUSSION

This case underscores the therapeutic value of *Shodhita Kasisadrava Basti* in treating *Arsha* (second-degree internal haemorrhoids), a condition recognized by *Acharya Sushruta* as one of the eight most severe diseases (*Ashtamahagada*). From an Ayurvedic standpoint, the patient's presentation reflected classic features of *Vata-Pittaja Arsha*, driven by impaired *Agni* (*Mandagni*), disturbed *Apana Vayu*, and poor lifestyle and dietary choices.

The *Kasisadrava* used in the *Basti* possessed *Lekhana* (scraping), *Rakta-Stambhaka* (haemostatic), and *Shodhana* (purificatory) actions, which aligned well with the underlying pathogenesis. Administering the therapy rectally allowed for localized absorption and deeper action in the *Guda Marga* (anal region).

Over a three-week treatment period

- Bleeding stopped completely by the second week.
- The prolapse pile mass reduced at the end of the treatment.
- Itching and discomfort were significantly improved the end of the treatment.

At the 45-day follow-up, the results were sustained—there was no recurrence of primary symptoms, and only mild constipation remained. This was managed through appropriate dietary guidance and possibly *Anulomana* herbs tailored to the patient's *Prakriti* (constitution).

The patient's outcome supports the use of localized *Shodhana Chikitsa* as an effective non-surgical approach for anorectal conditions. It highlights the potential of such interventions to offer symptom relief and prevent recurrence, especially where conservative management is preferred.

CONCLUSION

This case shows that using *Shodhita Kasisadrava Basti* in a planned and regular way helped a lot in treating *Arsha* (second-degree internal haemorrhoids). The treatment reduced bleeding, and prolapse, and helped improve the patient's overall comfort. Since there were no side effects or return of symptoms, it seems like a safe and gentle option in Ayurvedic care.

To keep the benefits going, it's important to follow a *Pathya-Apathya* (healthy diet), stay active, and maintain regular bowel habits. More research with a larger number of patients will help confirm these results and create clear treatment guidelines for others to follow.

REPORTS

ASSESSMENT WERE PERFORMED DAYS 1,07,14 and 21 USING PROCTOSCOPY TO EVALUATE REDNESS, SWELLING, BLEEDING & PROLAPSE

Day 14

Day 21

PREMSWARUP SWAMI MULTISPECIALITY HOSPITAL

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Adrees: Ahmedabad-Mehsana Highway, At&Po.-Saij, Ta.-Kalol, Dist.-Gandhinagar,
Gujarat-382725, Contact: +91-8866213131, Website:www.psmhospital.org

TEST REPORT

Name	Mr. Ketanbhai Rathva	Reg. No	020146/0024
Age/Sex	36 Years / Male	Reg. Date	02-Feb-2025 10:10 AM
Ref. By	Dr. Darshana Ramole	Collected On	02-Feb-2025 10:15 AM
Client Name		Report Date	02-Feb-2025 02:20 PM

Parameter	Result	Unit	Biological Ref. Interval
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COMPLETE BLOOD COUNT (CBC)
Specimen: EDTA blood

HB & RBC INDICES

Hemoglobin (SLS method)	14.2	g/dL	12.5 - 16.0
RBC Count (Electrical Impedance)	4.80	million/cmm	4.2 - 5.4
Hematocrit (Electrical Impedance)	45.20	%	37 - 47
MCV (Calculated)	83.22	fL	78 - 100
MCH (Calculated)	30.0	Pg	27 - 31
MCHC (Calculated)	31.86	%	30 - 35
RDW (Calculated)	14.40	%	11.5 - 14.0
PDW	16.4	%	10 - 17.9
MPV	7.8	fL	7.4 - 10.4
WBC Count (Flowcytometry)	5600	/cmm	4000 - 10500

DIFFERENTIAL COUNT (Manual By Microscopy)

Neutrophils (%)	62	%	42 - 75
Lymphocytes (%)	31	%	20 - 70
Eosinophils (%)	03	%	1 - 4
Monocytes (%)	04	%	2 - 8
Basophils (%)	00	%	0 - 2

PLATELET COUNT

Platelet Count	268000	/cmm	150000 - 450000
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ERYTHROCYTE SEDIMENTATION RATE

ESR (After 1 hour)	8	mm/hr	ESR AT 30 Min : 3-12 ESR AT 30 Min : 13-20
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BLOOD GROUPING & Rh TYPING

Blood Group	: " B "
Rh Factor	: " POSITIVE "

This is an Electronically Authenticated Report.

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Client Name		Report Date	02-Feb-2025 02:20 PM

COAGULATION PROFILE

TEST	RESULT	UNIT	REFERENCE INTERVAL
Bleeding Time	: 02:40	MINS	Up to 5 Mins.
Clotting Time	: 05:25	MINS	Up to 11 Mins.

BIOCHEMISTRY ANALYSIS

Random Blood Glucose (RBS)	: 94.00	mg/dl	GOD-POD	60 - 130 mg/dl
S. Creatinine	: 0.75	mg/dl	Jaffe's Kinetic	0.5 - 1.5 mg/dl

IMMUNOLOGY ANALYSIS

S.HBsAg (Australia Antigen) Kit	: NON REACTIVE	HEPACARD	Immunochromatography	NON REACTIVE
V.D.R.L.	: NON REACTIVE			NON REACTIVE
KIT	: SYPHICHECK		Immunochromatography	

LIMITATIONS OF THE PROCEDURE: 1. This is only a Screening test. All reactive samples should be confirmed by confirmatory test. Therefore for a definitive diagnosis, the patient's clinical history, symptomatology as well as serological data, should be considered. 2. False positive results can be obtained due to the presence of other antigens or elevated levels of RF factor.

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TEST REPORT

Name	Mr. Ketanbhai Rathva	Reg. No	020146/0024
Age/Sex	36 Years / Male	Reg. Date	02-Feb-2025 10:10 AM
Ref. By	Dr. Darshana Ramole	Collected On	05-Feb-2025 10:15 AM
Client Name		Report Date	05-Feb-2025 02:20 PM

IMMUNOLOGY ANALYSIS

TEST	RESULT	METHOD	REFERENCE INTERVAL
HIV ANTIBODY TEST			
HIV - 1	: NON REACTIVE		NON REACTIVE
HIV - 2	: NON REACTIVE		NON REACTIVE
KIT	: HIV 1&2 TRILINE	Immunochromatography	

LIMITATIONS OF THE TEST:

1. Following factors are found to cause false positive HIV antibody test results: Naturally occurring antibodies, Passive immunization, Leprosy, Renal Disorders, Tuberculosis, Myco-bacterium avium, Herpes simplex, Hypergamma-globulinemia, Malignant neoplasms, Rheumatoid arthritis, Tetanus vaccination, Autoimmune diseases, Blood Transfusion, Multiple myeloma, Haemophilia, Heat treated specimens, Lipemic serum, Anti-nuclear antibodies, T-cell leukocyte antigen antibodies, Epstein Barr virus, HLA antibodies and other retroviruses. 2. This is only a screening test. All samples detected reactive must be confirmed by using HIV Western Blot. 3. A non-reactive result does not exclude the possibility of exposure to or infection with HIV.

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